

A Sensitivity Analysis on Fuzzy Greek Parameters

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Greek parameters are important to analyze how European call and put option prices respond to changes in pricing parameters under uncertainty (Hull,2021).¹ Before developing the fuzzy Greeks for call and put options with the moving barrier, as in our paper “ A Coherent Fuzzy Framework for Pricing European Call Down-and-Out and European Put Up-and-Out Options under Moving Curve Barriers”, we describe the sensitivity analysis of these parameters in fuzzy approach so we can compare their behavior to the ones with moving barrier. Previous work on the option’s Greeks parameters is in (Chen et.all, 2019).² We define Coherent Fuzzy Numbers as in our paper as the following.

Definition A fuzzy number $\tilde{A} = (a_L, a_C, a_R)_{(\gamma_1, \gamma_2)} = ((1 - \rho_1)a_C, a_C, (1 + \rho_2)a_C)_{(\gamma_1, \gamma_2)}$, with $\gamma_1, \gamma_2 > 0$ and $0 \leq \rho_1, \rho_2 < 1$, is defined as a coherent triangular fuzzy number with two adaptive exponents and two adaptive supports, which has the center fuzzy number a_C , the left end point $a_L = (1 - \rho_1)a_C$, and the right end point $a_R = (1 + \rho_2)a_C$. Its membership function $\mu_{\tilde{A}}(x)$ is defined as follows.

$$\mu_{\tilde{A}}(x) = \begin{cases} \left(\frac{x - a_L}{a_C - a_L} \right)^{\gamma_1}, & a_L < x \leq a_C, \\ \left(\frac{a_R - x}{a_R - a_C} \right)^{\gamma_2}, & a_C \leq x < a_R, \\ 0, & \text{else.} \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

For the numerical simulation, Call and Put options parameters being used are $K = 100$, $T = 1$, $r = 0.1$, $\sigma = 0.25$, and $S(0) = 95$. The values of the coherent fuzzy numbers being used are in Table 1, which are intended to be the same with the ones in our paper.

Let \tilde{V} be a fuzzy option price. The Fuzzy Greeks being considered include

1. Fuzzy Delta $\tilde{\Delta}$ that measures the sensitivity of option prices to the price of the underlying asset, with the formula $\tilde{\Delta} = \frac{\partial \tilde{V}}{\partial S}$.

Table 1 Coherent Parameters Used in the Simulation

Parameter	Call	Put	r	σ
ρ_1	0.03	0.10	0.10	0.10
ρ_2	0.10	0.10	0.10	0.10
γ_1	0.50	0.50	0.50	0.50
γ_2	4.00	4.00	4.00	4.00

Fig 1 Fuzzy Delta interval for the European Call option

Fig 2 Fuzzy Delta interval for the European put option

Options with high absolute Delta values carry higher directional risk. Figures 1 and 2 show that the delta values increase smoothly and approaches one, for call option, or zero, for put option, as the underlying asset price rises. This result is consistent with classical option pricing theory, where an in-the-money call and put options become increasingly responsive to changes in the underlying asset value. Using values in Table 1, the fuzzy intervals are not clearly seen for each stock price.

2. Fuzzy Theta $\tilde{\Theta}$ that reflects the effect of the passage of time, with formula $\tilde{\Theta} = \frac{\partial \tilde{V}}{\partial \tau}$.

Fig 3 Fuzzy Theta interval for the European call option

Fig 4 Fuzzy Theta interval for the European put option

For $\tau = T - t$ decreases as time passes. For option buyers, the time value typically decreases, so Θ is generally negative. As the option loses value as it approaches maturity, a larger

negative Θ indicates greater time-decay risk.

- Fuzzy Vega \tilde{v} that measures sensitivity to volatility, with formula $\tilde{v} = \frac{\partial \tilde{V}}{\partial \sigma}$. An option with a

Fig 5 Fuzzy Vega interval for the European call option

Fig 6 Fuzzy Vega interval for the European Put option

high Vega is exposed to greater volatility risk. Figures 5 and 6 show that Fuzzy Vega initially increases, reaches a maximum level, and subsequently declines. This pattern reflects the well-established property that volatility has the greatest influence on option value when the option is close to the at-the-money region.

4. Fuzzy Rho $\tilde{\rho}$ that represents how the option price reacts to changes in the risk-free interest rate, with formula $\tilde{\rho} = \frac{\partial \tilde{V}}{\partial r}$.

A higher value of Rho of a long-term option can have a stronger effect on its present value and pricing. Figures 4 and 4 exhibit the expected positive relationship between option value and the risk-free interest rate.

The widths of the fuzzy intervals provide further insight into the propagation of uncertainty. Across all figures, the uncertainty bands are not uniform throughout the parameter domain. Wider intervals appear in regions where the Greeks change more rapidly, indicating that small perturbations in the input parameters can produce relatively large variations in the corresponding sensitivity measures. In contrast, narrower intervals are observed in more stable regions where the option sensitivities are less affected by parameter uncertainty. These findings highlight that uncertainty propagation is closely related to the nonlinear characteristics of the pricing model.

References

- 1 John C. Hull, *Options, Futures, and Other Derivatives*, Pearson, 11 ed. (2021).
- 2 Hong-Ming Chen, Cheng-Feng Hu, and Wei-Chang Yeh, “Option pricing and the greeks under gaussian fuzzy environments,” *Soft Computing* **23**(24), 13351–13374 (2019).